

**ПЕДАГОГИК ВА
ПСИХОЛОГИК
ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР**

ЯНВАРЬ, 2023

1-СОН

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PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDIES**

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ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ**

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НАУЧНО-ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
НОМЕР-1**

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ИЛМИЙ-АМАЛИЙ ЖУРНАЛ
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PROS AND CONS OF ONLINE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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ANNOTATION

This article is related to the introduction of online courses into the educational process. The main goal of the article is to identify the positive and negative aspects of online education. The importance and value of online education in the conditions of Uzbekistan is analyzed. As with everything, there are pros and cons, and this article discusses some of the issues with online education.

Keywords: online education, educational process, scientists, pros and cons, online courses, digital technologies, computer.

ПЛЮСЫ И ПРОТИВ ОНЛАЙН-КУРСОВ В ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ ПРОЦЕССЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Данная статья посвящена внедрению онлайн-курсов в учебный процесс. Основная цель статьи - выявить положительные и отрицательные стороны онлайн-образования. Анализируется важность и ценность онлайн-образования в условиях Узбекистана. Как и во всем, здесь есть свои плюсы и минусы, и в этой статье обсуждаются некоторые проблемы онлайн-образования.

Ключевые слова: онлайн-образование, образовательный процесс, ученые, плюсы и минусы, онлайн-курсы, цифровые технологии, компьютер.

TA'LIM JARAYONIDA ONLAYN KURSLARNING IJOBİY VA SALBIY TOMONLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqola ta'lim jarayoniga onlayn kurslarning joriy etilishi bilan bog'liq. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi onlayn ta'limning ijobiy va zaif tomonlarini aniqlashdir. O'zbekiston sharoitida onlayn ta'limni ahamiyati va dolzarligi tahlil qilinadi. Har narsani yaxshi va yomon tomoni bo'lgani kabi, onlayn ta'limda ham shunday muammolar haqida ushbu maqolada so'z yuritiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: onlayn ta'lim, ta'lim jarayoni, olimlar, ijobiy va salbiy tomonlari, onlayn kurslar, raqamli texnologiyalar, kompyuter.

Nowadays, it is difficult to imagine the educational process without the use of online courses. The rapid growth in the number of mass online courses is causing interest in them among educational organizations. Of course, a qualified teacher can have a very effective impact on students in traditional classes. However, when learning takes place in an online course, attention can also be monitored and encouraged through indirect communication. For this, you need to use only the appropriate tools: visual design of materials, course notifications and support, program and task construction logic, etc. Online education allows virtually any teacher to create a course that will be popular with students. In addition, if the specific features of the subject are not taken into account when introducing online education, students of special training, even an excellent course, can have a negative result. Proper organization of skills and processes is necessary not only for creating a course, but also for its implementation.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

The theoretical and practical issues of using online education teaching technologies, its didactic and methodical foundations, as well as the problems of using the online education process in our country, the variability of the educational content are researched by the scientists of our country A.Abduqadirov, N.Muslimov, U.Begimkulov, A.Hayitov, M.Lutfillaev, N.Tailakov, CIS scientists Ye.Polat, A.Andreev, N.Naydenova, G.Levkin, I.Varganova, N.Valyushina, R.Pimonov, N.Gavrilov, I.Zadorojnyaya, S.Berezhnaya, M.A. Malsheva, S. Bogdanova and foreign scientists A.Amadco, I.Allen, J.Seaman, D.Keegan, H.Kappel, B.Lehmann, J.Loeper, B.Holmberg, M.Dougiamas, P.Taylor.

At the same time, our scientists J.Yoldoshev, R..Djuraev, R.Ahlidinov, S.Turgunov, Kh.Rashidov, Sh.Qurbanov, U.Inoyatov, N.Rakmonkulova, R.Safarova, M.Yuldashev, scientists of the CIS, V.Gorshkova, I.Podlasi, A.Solojin studied this research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

One of the main tasks of the teacher is to create an educational space, and they also perform independent tasks for online courses [1, P.6]. Only here, this space is partially or completely virtual (depending on the chosen educational model: mixed or fully distance learning).

It is only necessary to understand the possibilities and limitations of the online format and you can start designing. Thus, this place in open online courses is built around the teacher. Research results confirm that charisma is a decisive factor in evaluating the quality of video lectures for online course participants. That is, the course is definitely created for students, and their goals and tasks are put first in the design. But the main element of this course is its authors, carriers of that "living" knowledge. Moreover, in an online format, particles of this knowledge can be delivered to a much larger audience than without using it. It is very important not only to give the material, but also to reserve it with some control. Otherwise, part of the audience coming to the session may not be ready for practice and laboratory work.

Advantages of online education include:

- coverage of a large number of students, auditoriums are not necessary;
- use of modern and interactive technologies to present theoretical material and perform assignments;
- mobility, mobility and training in 24/7 mode;
- the ability to study anywhere and anytime;
- variability and diversity;
- the opportunity to listen to lectures several times (if it is interesting or to clarify the details of the material);
- training for disabled people through online courses;
- the possibility of self-development, self-education;
- optimization of the educational process (reducing the teacher's communication load within reasonable limits);
- quality organization of not only auditorium but also independent work of students who are not always consistently and precisely controlled during the daytime education process;
- for the university - the possibility of placement and, as a result, an increase in the university's rating.

In addition, as part of the online course, students are in a comfortable environment, so they are less stressed when completing the control tasks, and they get the results and information about the mistakes made during the test faster. On the other hand, it is more difficult for the teacher to control how independently this work is performed [4]. Therefore, it is necessary to create tasks that can be performed without simply writing off the answer from the lecture materials, but only after fully understanding the topic.

The modern generation lives in a virtual space, so online courses are a good idea to combine their free time with studying, or in other words, to give them an opportunity to learn in an interesting and relevant place. Taking online courses can provide additional career guidance to prospective applicants, providing information to undergraduate and graduate students who have previously studied in a different field, as well as to all distance education students. At the same time, online education creates wide opportunities for joint activities of all participants of the educational process.

In addition to the advantages listed above, from our point of view, the following can be illustrated: online courses also help in teaching foreigners, because it is difficult for them to study in the general stream and there is no opportunity for the teacher to give them plenty of time because other students need attention too.

Optimizing the teacher's time is of great importance, allowing the time to be used for science or, if it is a teacher. A subject designer is a methodical work to complete already created material and improve the quality of teaching. In general, the power of online courses for a teacher is the opportunity to express oneself, to transfer one's experience to an unlimited number of students; for students, it is the availability of education, improvement of their skills, and the opportunity to establish new contacts for future cooperation.

If we talk about the weaknesses of online education (and there are many), then the following should be noted:

- time-consuming and high cost of creating online courses;
- loss of the ability of students to analyze and synthesize the material in online courses, it is given almost ready-made and you don't need to think about anything;
- the possibility of conducting several tests (as a result, the assessment does not adequately reflect the student's knowledge);
- problems with proctoring (authentication of students).
- therefore, not being able to control whether the announced student is actually studying in the course, that is, another student can complete the assignments for him/her instead;
- excessive formalization and regulation of education, restriction of its creative component (in some cases suppression);
- one-sided presentation of the educational material by the speaker, lack of "live" dialogue can distract the attention of the audience: usually during the lecture some questions, comments, additions, examples present the educational material and students "enliven" themselves (not every talented teacher has modern technical methods of keeping the attention of the audience). The lack of direct (personal) interaction between the teacher and the student (pupil), focusing more on acquiring knowledge, less on the formation of skills, does not allow the full implementation of a competency-based approach.

The lack of direct contact with the teacher can be considered a positive point, unless he/she has very high qualifications. For example, the lectures of a professor gather more audience than the lectures of an ordinary teacher. Often, teachers are specialized in their narrow subjects, and they require serious support from experts in modern pedagogical technologies, because the course can't be built if it does not conform to the structure of the Bologna system. We can agree with all these shortcomings, but with the appropriate energy, taking into account the specific characteristics of the educational sector and a smart approach to the development and use of an online course for a specific purpose, very good results can be achieved.

It should be noted that so far, no MOEC (massive online educational courses) can be compared with the work of a teacher at the initial stage, where a conceptual apparatus based on logical thinking is created. Independently organize your time, workplace, and a disciplined approach to the implementation of assignments is not for every student.

Some subjects, including a foreign language, require the formation of oral communication skills (especially spontaneous) through face-to-face communication with the teacher and other students, so in this case, a public online course is only can be a useful addition to the classroom. In fact, there is a problem with teaching foreign languages using online courses. In this field (although it uses many courses and they are popular), online learning opportunities are very limited, especially in the format of public online courses [2, P.7]. Both at the initial stage and at the later (intermediate and advanced) stages, only "live" communication and constant interaction with the teacher will help to achieve success in the correct acquisition of language material and the development of communicative competence.

At each stage of teaching a foreign language, the learning process should be saturated with speech exercises, which are a decisive factor in the practical acquisition of a foreign language [8, P.9]. Students have to make presentations, participate in discussions and talk to each other in a foreign language. It should be noted that the measurement of students' knowledge, skills and abilities is not a foreign language test, but one of the educational exercises. Only when asking questions, answering them, talking with the teacher or in "student-student" pairs, identifying the main topic of the proposed material, commenting on it, etc. it is possible to determine the student's level of readiness for further use of a foreign language. This is especially true if the student is learning a foreign language for use in oral and written communication in the next professional field (first of all, when it comes to professions related to intellectual work), as well as for studying abroad [5]. In addition, the weakest areas of speech communication that are very difficult to work online are phonetics, writing and speaking, because they all require discussion, feedback, physical control.

At the same time, it should be noted that the formation and automation of certain skills in the use of certain units of grammar, the development of reading and listening skills can and should be done online [7]. Since such courses and developments already exist, it is necessary to train faculty to use these materials and involve them in their further optimization, as well as to develop new materials in this field.

In our opinion, online learning currently has more weaknesses than strengths. While it is still possible to provide information to the audience in theory, it is problematic in practice. In addition, it is impossible to control their knowledge fully. Passing the test does not mean that the student has mastered the learning material correctly (you can pass a test based on logic rather than knowledge). We regret to say that the quality of higher education has decreased due to the lack of "live" communication in the academic environment. The "threats" of online education include a reduction in the number of teachers who are not fully qualified in computer technology, but who teach their discipline at a highly professional level in the traditional system.

If there is an opportunity for personal communication between the teacher and the student (and currently it exists), this opportunity should be implemented as much as possible, first of all, by increasing the class hours. Personal communication between a teacher and a student, in addition to the informational component, also includes educational moments, unfortunately, are almost forgotten now, which turn education into a service sector. Perhaps online learning is appropriate for deeply motivated students. However, in practice, you often find it difficult to manage your time and find the information you need effectively. In addition, virtual reality cannot teach teamwork that is necessary in real life.

In conclusion, it should be important that online courses for the teacher are a valuable source of methodological experience, generally positive. This experience is especially useful if teacher plans to create his own online course. However, there are many subjects where online courses cannot replace "live" interaction with a teacher. In modern conditions, as a supplement to classical education, online education is relevant and necessary, but only as a supplement.

Thus, the analysis of the problem of introducing online education into the educational process made it possible to identify its strengths and weaknesses. As shown, the development potential of online courses offers users new types of research, self-education, an intellectual activity. In addition to traditional learning, they help to develop an intellectually and professionally developed person, independence, provide access to new sources of educational information. The author's conclusion about the didactic potential of online courses is that their use provides an opportunity to form new forms of independent cognitive activity and helps to use Internet resources effectively.

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